

Domain	Cropping practices	Pest constraints
A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High fertilizer input Some manure Previous crop: wheat predominant Transplanted rice Medium-high yield 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Deadhearts Whiteheads Armyworms Rice bugs Sheath blight Sheath rot Neck blast
B	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Low fertilizer input Some manure Diverse previous crops Water stress often high Transplanted rice predominant Short cycle Low yield 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Glume discoloration (Leaf blast)
C	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Low fertilizer input No manure Previous crop: wheat only Medium-low water stress Transplanted or direct seeded rice Long-cycle varieties 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Weeds above the rice canopy Glume discoloration
D	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No fertilizer Fallow 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Deadhearts Whiteheads Sheath rot

2. A correspondence analysis of patterns of cropping practices, yield levels, and pest profiles.

crop management practices.) It indicates that recommendation domains associated with the corresponding injury profiles can actually be delineated.

A recommendation domain should be seen in terms of the combination of crop management practices, rather than in terms of spatial proximity, and need not be continuous at the farm level (Fig. 2). For example, two neighboring fields may belong to different recommendation domains.

This approach provides a framework for the current hypothesis-testing process, where the actual damage due to pest combinations is being measured in farmers' field experiments in Uttar Pradesh and in crop loss data base experiments at IRRI. ■

Empirical estimates of yield and pest potentials of farmers' rainfed lowland ricefields

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Data on crop performance, including disease, insect, weed, and other pest severities; yield; soil conditions; and crop and pest management practices, were collected in field surveys and holistic experiments with integrated crop protection treatments at four rainfed lowland sites in the Mekong Delta, Vietnam, and northeast Thailand in 1992. At each site, 4-5 farmers' fields were selected and subdivided into plots receiving either no pest control, pest control according to farmers' practices, or fungicide and insecticide applications 4-5 times during the growing season. Fields were visited repeatedly during the growing season for data collection. Data were used to develop simple methods for estimating yield potentials of sites, pest-yield effects, and pest proneness.

Target yields (Y_t) were computed based on a model developed and parameterized by Neue in 1985: $Y_t = 0.05 FN_e - 0.000225 FN_e^2 + 0.05 FN_e N_t + (2.4152 N_t - 6.0882 N_t^2) d_r$, where N_t = % soil N, d_r = effective rooting depth in cm, and FN_e = effective uptake of N fertilizer in kg/ha: $FN_e = 1.193 FN^{0.9}$, where FN = fertilizer N in kg/ha. N_t was estimated based on total soil C content, assuming a C-N ratio of 10.

Because a portion of the total C and N in soils is effectively inert due to chemical nature and organomineral interactions, the model was modified by a relationship independently found by Gaunt that accounts for protection of soil C and N by clay: $N_t = (C - 0.016L)/10$, where C = % soil carbon and L = % clay content of soil. A variable (GPEST) representing the combined maximum severity levels of pest intensity on

Results of regression analyses to explain yield and pest intensity in farmers' fields at rainfed lowland sites in Vietnam and northeast Thailand.^a

Dependent variable	Variable in equation	Slope	Standard error of slope	Beta value
YIELD	Y_t	.616	.044	1.033
	GPEST	-.332	.073	-.333
	constant	2.763	.146	
	$R^2 = .72; n = 93$			
GPEST	SAND	-.021	.004	-.507
	Y_t	.342	.071	.571
	$Y_t * P * K$	-.127	.036	-.355
	constant	2.402	.263	
	$R^2 = .62; n = 93$			

^aYIELD = yield in t/ha; Y_t = target yield; GPEST = pest intensity on generative plant organs and/or whole tillers; SAND = % soil sand content; P = ppm available soil P; K = meq K/100 g soil. All variables in the equations are significant at $P = 0.001$ according to *T*-test. Both regression models are significant at $p = 0.0001$ according to *F*-test.

generative plant organs and/or whole tillers was computed: $GPEST = \ln\{[1 - (1 - x_1/100)(1 - x_2/100)...(1 - x_n/100)]100 + 1\}$, where $x_1 \dots x_n = \%$ maximum severity level of the respective disease or pest damage type. Pest damage types and diseases considered for computing GPEST were panicle blast, dirty panicle, stem rot, foot rot, tungro virus, false smut, other panicle damage, stem borer deadhearts and whiteheads, and cut tillers due to other pests.

In multivariate regression analyses, yield variation was explained by Y_t (target yield) and GPEST with $R^2 = 0.72$. Y_t had a much greater relative value for predicting yield than did GPEST (see table). Variability of GPEST could be explained by parameters of soil fertility and water-holding capacity such as soil sand content (SAND), Y_t , and a term describing interaction among Y_t , soil phosphorus (P), and soil potassium content (K) with $R^2 = 0.62$. When predicted values are plotted vs actual

values, data points for the different sites blend fairly well into a homogeneous data cloud along the 1:1 line (see figure).

The results indicate that it is possible to quantify rice yield expectations for rainfed lowland areas based on parameters that characterize soil fertility corresponding to physiological potential yield, although parameterization of Y_t might need further adjustment and the role of water problems needs investigation and appropriate consideration. Yield expectations can be further adjusted for pest damage effects through relatively simple single equation-type models. Pest damage expectations might be quantifiable based on parameters of soil fertility and water-holding capacity, because high soil N (and in some cases drought stress) increases the susceptibility of the rice crop to pest attacks.

Further analyses will aim to identify key biotic constraints for higher yields, develop simple yet robust rules for predicting the proneness of sites for

Actual YIELD (t/ha)

Actual GPEST (% ln [y+1])

a) Observed yield (YIELD) and b) pest intensity during the generative phase (GPEST) vs values estimated by MRA for farmers' fields at rainfed lowland site ^a in northeast Thailand and Vietnam ^b.

^aSites: Thailand 1= Khon Kaen, 2= Phai Mai, 3= Sakon Nakhon, 4= Ubon; Vietnam 5= Bac Lieu, 6= Ca Mau, 7= Long An, 8= Soc Trang. \$ = multiple occurrence of data points. ^bSee Table 1 for regression equations and definition of variables.

specific pest-loss problems, and define agroecological domains for extrapolation of knowledge and technology for disease management in rainfed lowland rice. ■

Genetic manipulation of *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae*

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Introduction of plasmid DNA into *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae* (Xoo),

the rice bacterial blight pathogen, can be routinely and efficiently achieved by electrotransformation or by conjugation using a biparental mating system. Mobilizable plasmids with broad-host range, such as pUFRO27, pUFRO47, pHM1(cosmid), pUFRO34(cosmid), pUFRO43(cosmid), and pLAFR3(cosmid) are convenient vectors that are compatible with Xoo. Electrotransformation requires

a costly instrument, the electro-porator, but is fast, easy, and good for small-scale cloning experiments. Biparental matings between Xoo and *E. coli* strain S17-1, which has a mobilization gene in the chromosome, do not require expensive equipment and are excellent for large-scale experiments, such as screening a genomic library. With this system, a helper plasmid is not needed to mobi-